

Does Total Factor Productivity Tilt the Nexus between Human Capital Development and Economic Growth in Selected Sub-Saharan African Countries?

L. Shobowale

Department of Economics, Adeleke University, Nigeria
shobowale.lateef@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng,

B. C. Olopade (PhD)

Centre for Economic Policy and Development Research (CEPDeR).
olopadebosede@adelekeuniversity.edu.ng

J. S. Ojewumi

Department of Economics, Adeyemi Federal University of Education, Nigeria
ojewumij@s@aceondo.edu.ng
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Abstract

The study investigated the interactive effects of human capital development and selected total factor productivity components (technology and infrastructure) on economic growth in selected Sub-Saharan African Countries (SSA) during the period 1981-2020. The study made use of panel data of the selected SSA countries using Pooled OLS Model, Fixed Effects and Random Effects Models, subjecting them to Hausman test. The augmented Solow growth model was employed and the study variables were economic growth rate; human capital development - proxied by Human Development Index (HDI), physical infrastructure – proxied by Physical Infrastructure Index (PII), technology – proxied by Research and Development (R&D), growth of labour force, share of private investment in GDP, trade openness, financial openness and share of total government expenditure. The result showed that the joint effect of human capital development and technology on economic growth was positive and statistically significant. The joint effect of human capital development and physical infrastructure was positive on economic growth. The study recommended government spending and massive investment on education, health, physical infrastructure and technology.

Keywords: Economic growth, Human capital development, Physical infrastructure, Technology, Total factor productivity, Sub-Saharan Africa

Introduction

For decades, both theoretical and empirical study has given economic growth increasing amounts of focus (Shobowale et al., 2022). This is in part due to the lack of a unifying economic theory and the reductionist strategy taken by mainstream economics to the problem. The role of various variables in determining economic performance and development is discussed in a number of partial theories despite the absence of a unifying theory. Economic growth is defined as the change in the output of a nation over time (Shobowale et al., 2022).

Additionally, some factors are considered crucial in the growth process, such as human capital development and total factor productivity (technology and infrastructure). In general, people are regarded as the most important factor in rising productivity and economic development. This is because machinery and technology are creations of human ingenuity that can be used to boost output (Shobowale et al., 2022). Therefore, the success of any productive program relies on human ingenuity and creativity (Pelinescu, 2015). Infrastructure alone is not sufficient to bring about long-term development. The justification for this is that without human capital, human progress would be minimal, similar to how plants, offices, computers, automated equipment, internet systems, and all other facilities that any nation may install would remain unproductive without human efforts and guidance. Similarly, human capital may not function to its full potential without the infrastructure and technology required to boost and improve output (Ohanyere et al., 2019). As a result, sustaining economic growth in Africa continues to be one of the major obstacles to worldwide development, and little is known about the factors that specifically affect economic growth in Africa (Anyanwu, 2014). Oladeji and Adebayo (1996), cited in Anyanwu et al. (2015), claim that human resources are

essential to progress and deserving of development. They are the means and, more significantly, the ends that must be employed in order to advance the economy.

In light of this, achieving rapid and sustained economic development is the main goal of policies in many developing nations, including Africa. Such rapid and sustained economic growth is essential if not sufficient for overall development and increases people's opportunities for creativity and productivity. It enables people to accomplish other significant goals for themselves and their societies, such as preventing widespread poverty and hardship. Additionally, it generates funds for promoting healthcare, education, and other Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) that the world has pledged to (Anyanwu, 2014). According to UNDP (2006), SSA is plagued by a variety of poverty-related issues. The majority of SSA nations' Human Development Index (HDI) scores have stagnated or decreased since 1990, making it the world's poorest territory. A large portion of SSA nations can also be described as neopatrimonial, where clientelism and unofficial patronage networks are the foundation of political relationships and power. The development of an environment that is conducive to fighting poverty is undermined by poor governance, which includes weak formal institutions and the rule of law, poorly conceived and executed policies, insufficient service delivery, and high levels of corruption. Therefore, it is necessary for the government of SSA countries to be transparent, responsive, accountable, and corrupt free to attain a high human development index.

Several studies have been conducted at the empirical level, but the numbers of studies on SSA countries are few. The studies also have a pitfall or gap. For instance, studies like Bokana and Akinola (2017), Danquah and Ouattara (2014), as well as Zelleke et al. (2013) investigated the contributions of human capital development and total factor productivity to economic growth in selected SSA countries. One of the major pitfalls common to these studies is that they focused more on the direct effect of human capital development on productivity growth and the adoption of technology without considering the interactive effects of human capital development and selected total factor productivity components (technology and infrastructure) which serve as the complementary factors needed to achieve economic growth. Also, a contribution to knowledge is expected to be made in this area of research, bringing to the fore how such factors as technology and infrastructure could moderate the nexus between human capital development and economic growth. To scholars and researchers in the field of study, outcomes from the study would help deepen understanding of the role of human capital development in economic growth. The research makes the important claim that increasing human capital alone is insufficient to generate the required economic growth. Along with human capital, other complementary variables like infrastructure and technology must be taken into consideration. Given this, relevant empirical evidence from the study would provide necessary inputs for requisite policy formulation.

Research objective

- i. The specific objective of the study is to investigate the interactive effect of human capital development and each of the two components of total factor productivity on economic growth in the selected countries over the study period.

Conceptual clarification

Investments in education, health, on-the-job training, and migration that increase a person's productivity in the labor market and non-market activities are collectively referred to as human capital (Olopade et al., 2019). It has been said that the goal or end goal of development is the development of human capital. It's a means of realising people's potential by expanding their potential. And this necessarily implies the empowerment of people, enabling them to participate actively in their own development (Ohanyere et al., 2019). Human capital development can also be known as human capital formations or Human-Resource development. The process of acquiring and growing the population of people with the education, experience, and skills necessary for any country's economic success is known as "human capital development" (Awolusi, 2019). It makes it

possible for other resources to be used as effectively as possible to spur growth and development (Adeyemi & Ogunsola, 2016).

Basically, the human development index, a composite index, is used to evaluate Human Capital Development (HDI). This measure includes elements related to health, knowledge, and standard of living, such as anticipated years of schooling, life expectancy at birth, and quality of life as a proxy, respectively (Akinlosotu, 2020). TFP, or total factor productivity, is frequently regarded as the main driver of GDP growth rate. Labour inputs, physical capital, and human and human capital are additional contributing elements. Total factor productivity gauges any lingering increases in an industry's or country's overall output that cannot be explained by the accumulation of conventional inputs like labour and capital (Sickles & Zelenyuk, 2019).

Economic growth can be described in two different ways, according to Guru (2016). Economic growth can be characterised in one manner as consistent annual increases in the real national income of an economy over an extended period of time. In other terms, economic growth is the upward trend in the net national product at constant prices. As a result, economic growth can be defined as the increase in the nation's output over time.

South of the Sahara is where Sub-Saharan Africa is geographically located on the continent of Africa. It includes all African nations and territories that are entirely or partly south of the Sahara, according to the United Nations. The SSA consists of 46 countries and 15 were selected, which can be categorised into four regions, i.e. West, East, Central and Southern Africa. Countries fall into four categories based on their HDI: very high, high, medium, and low human development. South Africa represents the high human development economies; Equatorial Guinea, Angola, Kenya, Zimbabwe, Republic of Congo, Cameroon, Ghana and Zambia represents the medium human development economies; while Nigeria, Tanzania, Senegal, Rwanda, Uganda and Cote d'Ivoire represents the low human development economies. It also evaluates whether the difference in human development index rates has joint effects on public spending in this economy and how it has impacted economic growth.

African economies have a lot of room to expand their production potential due to the presence of an educated and healthy labour population. Numerous empirical works have sought to include state spending on education (Pelinescu, 2015). Public spending on health and education is anticipated to have a positive effect on human capital through improved economic performance in African nations, as shown in Figure 1, which depicts the flow path of the directional impact. Nigeria's education spending usually performs much worse than the United Nations' recommended level of 26% of the national budget (CBN, 2009). There are also numerous references to the WHO suggestion that nations spend 5% of their GDP on health, a recommendation that was never officially accepted and has little foundation (Savedoff, 2003).

Government policies have a significant influence on the fiscal policy framework and the effective allocation of funds for infrastructure development, both of which are critical to HCD. Enhancing people's abilities and production productivity requires better institutional quality. This is so that equitable development chances are created by excellent institutions (Balcerza & Pietrzak, 2016). Infrastructure can directly affect human development by providing necessary services like portable electricity and water, as well as indirectly by promoting economic growth, opening up new income generating opportunities for the most vulnerable groups, and enhancing governance (Sapkota, 2014). Government spending on innovations, research, and development (R & D) is another crucial factor in achieving growth because it boosts output.

Figure 1: The relationship among human capital development, total factor productivity and economic growth
Source: Adapted from Shuaibu and Oladayo (2016)

Theoretical review

The Keynesian Harrod-Domar growth model serves as the foundation for the first neo-classical growth model, the Solow growth model. The Solow model is an exogenous model of long-run economic growth that examines how variations in population growth, savings rate, and technological advancement affect changes in the quantity of output in an economy over time (economic growth). Technical advancement, which is referred to as an exogenous factor, was found to have had a major influence in studies.

According to Solow (1956), despite the fact that an economy has limited resources in terms of labour and capital, technology can make an unlimited contribution, making technological advancement the primary driver of economic progress. The model offers a helpful framework for comprehending how capital deepening and technical advancement interact to affect the growth rate of production per worker. The two inputs to production, capital and labour, are compensated for their marginal products. The Solow growth model is constructed around the Cobb-Douglas production function, production at time t is:

$$Y_t = K_t^\alpha (A_t L_t)^{1-\alpha} \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \beta = 1 - \alpha \dots \dots \dots (4.1)$$

Where Y_t – Output level, K_t – Physical Capital Stock, L_t – Labour endowment, and A_t – level of technology, all at time ‘t’ respectively. By the a priori restriction $0 < \alpha < 1$, solow assumes that each individual inputs exhibits positive but diminishing marginal product – a lower stock of a given input yields higher a marginal product and vice-versa.

The Solow-Swan Model's glaring flaw is its inability to explain what drives technical advancement. The model indicates that advancements in technology support economic growth, but it does not

explain how this happens. (The rate is set exogenously). Slow (1957) argued that knowledge created by research and development outside the realm of the capitalist system such as looking into public research institutes was the source of technological advancement. The Mankiw, Romer and Weil (1992) model is an expansion of the Solow model.

Mankiw et al. (1992) add to this by saying that Solow's model provides more understanding of how improving human capital affects economic growth. The model includes a component of human capital as the determining element of long-term economic growth, expanding Solow's framework, which concentrates on exogenous technical progress. This theory's proponents contended that combining physical and human resources boosts productivity, highlighting the need of increasing human capital in quickening economic growth. (Attahir et al., 2020). According to Mankiw et al. (1992), human capital boosts a country's ability to create new technologies (domestically). Human capital is disregarded by the Solow growth model. The model was expanded to include human capital by Mankiw et al. (1992). Therefore, the production function now becomes: $Y_t = K_t^\alpha H_t^\beta (A_t L_t)^{1-\alpha-\beta}$ $\alpha + \beta < 1$ (2.2)

Where Y_t – Output level, K_t – Physical Capital Stock, H_t – stock of Human Capital, L_t – Labour endowment, and A_t – level of technology, all at time ‘t’ respectively. The parameters α and β are the output elasticity with respect to physical and human capital (shares of physical and human capital in total income), respectively. The a priori restriction that $\alpha + \beta < 1$, implies that there is a decreasing return to produce factors of production. The three key assumptions allowing this formulation are that: output is used for either consumption or investment in both human and physical capital; people invest in human capital just as they invest in physical capital; and human capital depreciates at the same constant rate δ as physical capital (Mankiw et al., 1992).

Methodology

The Mankiw et al. (1992) augmented Solow model was adopted as the theoretical framework for this study. The Solow framework, which emphasises exogenous technical advancement, is expanded by the model to take into account a component of human capital as the main driver of long-term economic growth. It is against this background the usual production function has been extended from two inputs: Labour and Capital. Hence the production function is expressed as follows:

$$Y = f(K, L, H) \tag{5.1}$$

Where: Y: total output, K: capital stock, L: Labour resources (unskilled labour), H: Human capital (skilled labour).

$$RGDPg_{it} = C_0 + \alpha INV_{it} + \lambda LFG_{it} + \beta HG_{it} + \psi_1 TG_{it} + \psi_2 PI_{it} + \phi_1 HG_{it} \cdot TG_{it} + \phi_2 HG_{it} \cdot PI_{it} + \psi_3 TOP + \psi_4 FOP + \psi_5 SGE + U_{it} \tag{5.2}$$

Where: $RGDPg_{it}$: Real GDP Growth (RGDPg), INV_{it} : % of Share of Private Investment in GDP (INV), LFG_{it} : Labour Force Growth (LFG), HG_{it} : Human Development Index (HDI), TG_{it} : Research and Development (R&D), PI_{it} : Physical Infrastructure Index, TOP : Trade Openness, FOP : Financial Openness, SGE : Share of Total Government Expenditure and U_{it} : the error term.

Result and discussion

Interactive effects of human capital development, technology and infrastructure

The available panel data models for this study are Pooled OLS Model, Fixed Effects and Random Effects Model. Table 6.1 shows Panel unit root test results for all the study variables. By the Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC) and Im, Peasaran and Shin (IPS) W-statistic tests, all the variables were stationary at level and were integrated of order zero, I(0). This means there is no long run relationship. Although this result permits the use of OLS, Table 1 indicates that the fixed effects model was better than Pooled OLS Model while the result of Hausman test in Table 2 proved that the Fixed effects model was the most appropriate option for the estimation of model on the

interactive effects of human capital development and each of technology, physical infrastructure on economic growth as indicated in the equation (1).

The value of adjusted was 0.9653 which indicated that approximately 96.7 percent of the variation in the dependent variable was explained by explanatory variables consisting of the right-hand side model, reflecting a good fit for the model. Hence, the estimated model was reasonably well behaved and fits the data well. This finding is in line with Uwatt (2002) who examined how human capital affects economic growth and asserted that physical capital had a positive effect on economic growth. The F-statistics report ($F= 445.41, p < 0.05$) showed that the result was statistically significant as the probability value of F-Statistics was less than 5%.

The interactive explanatory variables such as (HC *TG) and (HC * PI) exhibited a positive and statistically significant in line with the a priori expectation. This indicated the validity of the study that using human capital alone may not really generate the necessary growth in an economy but with the infusion of technology, physical infrastructure coupled with enabling environment enhanced economic growth.

Human capital contributed positively to economic growth. It induced economic growth by 0.11 in the long run ($t=2.74, p<0.05$). The sign of the estimated coefficient was positive and was highly significant. It showed that an enhanced human capital development is expected to raise the national income level of the country and thereby enhance economic prosperity. Besides, in the long run, investment had a positive effect on economic growth. The coefficient estimate of investment was 556.93 and was statistically significant at a 5% level of significance ($t=8.67, p<0.05$).

In addition, the interactive effect of human capital and technology on economic growth showed that the country in Sub-Saharan countries would achieve a reasonable level of growth when human capital is incorporated with technology. The interactive effect had 0.14 effects on the economic growth with a t-value of 7.85. It is expected that human capital requires technology in modern-day economic growth parlance. According to Neoclassical economic growth, technology enhances the labour and capital contribution to economic growth. The level of technological advancement of any country will surely determine its labour productivity.

The coefficient of the interactive effect of human capital and physical infrastructures indicated that the interaction of the two variables contributed positively to economic growth and was statistically significant at 5 percent level of significance ($t=8.96 p<0.05$). This indicated that the variable exerted a positive and significant effect on long-run change in the country's economy. In addition, financial openness influenced the economic growth of the Sub-Saharan countries positively with a coefficient of 75.13 which was statistically significant and indicated a reasonable contribution to economic growth ($t=6.77, p<0.05$). In the same vein, the share of total government expenditure had a positive effect on economic growth at a 5% level of significance. The high level of significance implies that increasing the share of total government expenditure could lead to employment in the short run as well as in the long run.

Table 1: Panel unit root test table

Variable	Levin, Lin & Chu t*		Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat		
	Statistics	p-value	Statistics	p-value	
SGE	-3.24105	0.0006	-4.52857	0.0000	I(0)

PI	-18.2624	0.0000	-19.9067	0.0000	I(0)
LFG	-20.4385	0.0000	-18.4080	0.0000	I(0)
RGDP	-3.71286	0.0000	-4.05625	0.0000	I(0)
FOP	-5.10733	0.0000	-4.59209	0.0000	I(0)
TG	-12.3408	0.0000	-13.1882	0.0000	I(0)
HC	-3.02290	0.0000	-4.15147	0.0000	I(0)
INV	-18.4728	0.0000	-9.72571	0.0000	I(0)
TOP	-22.7300	0.0000	-21.4315	0.0000	I(0)

Sources: Author's compilation (2022)

Table 2: Redundant fixed effects tests

Redundant Fixed Effects Tests			
Test cross-section fixed effects			
Effects Test	Statistic	d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section F	90.9453	(14,559)	0.0000
Cross-section Chi-square	581.5231	14	0.0000

Table 3: Hausman test

Correlated Random Effects - Hausman Test	
Test cross-section random effects	

Test Summary	Chi-Sq. Statistic	Chi-Sq. d.f.	Prob.
Cross-section random	129.2928	10	0.0000

Sources: Author's compilation (2022)

Table 4: Interactive effects of human capital development, technology and infrastructure

	Fixed Effect		
	Coeff	t-value	p-value
HC	0.1161	2.7475	0.0063
LFG	-82.5289	-2.9882	0.0030
INV	556.9318	8.6767	0.0000
HC*TG	0.1447	7.8509	0.0000
HC*PI	6.9817	8.9685	0.0000
TG	0.6265	6.5738	0.0000
PI	-97.6708	-5.3569	0.0000
TOP	1.9897	0.1671	0.8674
FOP	75.1367	6.7724	0.0000
SGE	72.5562	3.3745	0.0008
C	-88870.25	-6.8223	0.0000
R-squared	0.9675		
Adjusted R-squared	0.9653		
F-statistic	445.4164		
Prob(F-statistic)	0.0000		

Sources: Author's compilation (2022)

Discussion of findings

The analysis of the results of this study reveals several dimensions of the relationship between the human capital development, infrastructure and technology on economic growth in selected SSA

countries. For instance, the result of labour force growth exhibits a negative relationship with economic growth, which is not in accordance with the a priori expectation. To explain this, the Lewis model of unlimited supply of labour laid emphasis on the effect of labour force growth and the need to absorb the excess supply of labour through vocational training, education and proper health care system. The Lewis model believes that many underdeveloped countries including most SSA countries have unlimited supply of labour due to surplus population. Therefore, in order to reduce the excess labour force, there's need to absorb the labour force growth by converting it to human capital through vocational training, education and health, which in turns bring about positive impact on economic growth been the basis of the study.

Additionally, given the significance of Human Capital Development (HCD) to achieving the overall goal of achieving rapid and sustainable economic growth and development, the necessity of making significant investments in the country's educational sector with the aim of providing the necessary infrastructure, personnel, incentives for teachers, researchers, students, and other sector actors via scholarships, opportunities for self-advancement, etc., cannot be overemphasised. Furthermore the result also stressed the importance of physical infrastructure as a significant tools needed in collaboration with human capital in order to achieve the needed growth in an economy. In view of this, interactive effect between human capital and technology shows a positive and significant effect on economic growth. The implication of this is that, technology alone cannot provide the needed growth in an economy without the support of human capital. Human capital also may not really perform to a large extent without infrastructure and technology needed to increase and enhance productivity (Ohanyere et al., 2019).

Conclusion

The interactive effects of human capital development, technology and infrastructure on economic growth in SSA countries validate the purpose of the study. The study emphasis that human capital alone is not sufficient to provide growth but creating enabling environment and providing requisite physical infrastructure and technology will enhance economic growth. The research is limited to a period of forty years which is long enough to assess the interactive effect of human capital development and total factor productivity on economic growth in SSA countries. It is worthy to know that every research work possess a lot of challenges and limitations, but however, the difficulties encountered include the collection of data's for the countries under study. Furthermore, the study can be further researched in several ways by using other estimation techniques, other variables to capture human capital development for example, productivity, nutrition and household consumption. The years of estimation can be extended, it can be quarterly or monthly and it can further be researched by ECOWAS and other oil producing countries in the world. Lastly, significant research needs to be done in this area to provide more data for use in the analysis of human development index in developing nations.

Policy recommendation

Given the findings which have emanated from this study, the following policy recommendations are made:

- (1) The government should make investments in health, education, and vocational training to absorb the extra labour force in SSA nations. By doing this, we turn the raw labour into human capital, which is crucial since the theory holds that the more human capital there is, the more an economy will flourish. As a result, the economy benefits from the surplus of labour that has been turned into human capital through education, training, and health.
- (2) The government should increase its spending on technology, infrastructure and also provide enabling environment as it is paramount for human capital development to actualise its full potentials.

- (3) In order to support the economic growth of SSA nations through the development of human capital, health care and education should be accessible to and affordable for the average member of society.

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